

Morphofunctional Changes After Sleeve Gastrectomy and Very Low Calorie Diet in an Animal Model of Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease

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Abstract

Background Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is the most prevalent chronic liver disease and is found in 70% of obese people. The evidence available to date suggests that bariatric surgery could be an effective treatment by reducing weight and also by improving metabolic complications in the long term. This work aimed to compare, in a diet-induced NAFLD animal model, the effect of both sleeve gastrectomy (SG) and very-low calorie diet (VLCD).

Methods Thirty-five Wistar rats were divided into control rats (n = 7) and obese rats fed a high-fat diet (HFD). After

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10 weeks, the obese rats were subdivided into four groups: HFD (n = 7), VLCD (n = 7), and rats submitted to either a sham operation (n = 7) or SG (n = 7). Both liver tissue and blood samples were processed to evaluate steatosis and NASH changes in histology (Oil Red, Sirius Red and H&E); presence of endothelial damage (CD31, Moesin/p-Moesin, Akt/p-Akt, eNOS/p-eNOS), oxidative stress (iNOS) and fibrosis (α SMA, Col1, PDGF, VEGF) proteins in liver tissue; and inflammatory (IL6, IL10, MCP-1, IL17 α , TNF α), liver biochemical function, and hormonal (leptin, ghrelin, visfatin and insulin) alterations in plasma.

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Results Both VLCD and SG improved histology, but only SG induced a significant weight loss, improved endothelial damage, and decreased cardiovascular risk by reducing insulin resistance (IR), leptin, total cholesterol, and triglyceride levels. There were no relevant variations in the inflammatory and fibrosis markers. **Conclusion** Our study suggests a slight superiority of SG over VLCD by improving not only the histology but also the IR and cardiovascular risk markers related to NAFLD.

Keywords Fatty liver disease . Very low calorie diet . Sleeve gastrectomy . Inflammation . Liverfibrosis . Endothelial damage . Bariatric surgeryanimal model

Introduction

Obesity has more than doubled globally since 1980 and, even though it is a preventable condition, its incidence continues to grow. It is part of the metabolic syndrome (MS), which, apart from hypertension, dyslipidemia, central obesity, and insulin resistance (IR), can also associate other conditions including its hepatic manifestation, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) [1, 2].

NAFLD is characterized by excessive hepatic fat accumulation, associated with IR. It is the most common liver disorder in Western countries, affecting 17–46% of adults [3]. It is found in 70% of obese subjects but also has been found in 10–15% of normal weight individuals [4]. It includes two distinct conditions with different prognoses: non-alcoholic fatty liver (NAFL), which consists in the presence of simple steatosis, and non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), which includes inflammation, fibrosis and, eventually, cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) [5].

Neither the etiology nor the pathogenesis of NAFLD is fully understood, as it is a complex disease modulated by numerous mechanisms, including metabolic, genetic, environmental, and gut microbial factors [6, 7]. There is no definitive treatment either. The most effective treatment for NAFLD is so far weight reduction. In this sense, there are many proposals for NAFLD treatment: diet and lifestyle changes, antiobesity and antioxidant drugs, insulin sensitizers, and bariatric surgery [3, 5, 6].

Both clinical and experimental studies have shown that diet and lifestyle changes can reduce liver fat and improve NAFL and NASH, and thus they continue to be the first line of treatment [8–10]. However, their long-term success rate is limited [11].

Bariatric surgery is the most effective method for achieving substantial, sustained weight loss, and it also improves metabolic complications with stable long-term results. It has been proposed

as a treatment for NAFLD in patients unresponsive to lifestyle changes [3, 6]. Moreover, there is initial evidence showing that it can reduce liver fat and even improve necroinflammation and fibrosis in histology [5, 12, 13].

No solid data on the comparative effects of different bariatric procedures on liver fat are available in humans. The majority of papers assessing histological improvements are cohort studies in patients treated with a Roux-en-Y gastric bypass (RYGB). However, functional or histological evidence of the effects of other procedures such as sleeve gastrectomy (SG) on NAFLD remains scant. It is believed that, in addition to inducing significant weight loss and hormonal changes that could be beneficial in ameliorating NAFLD, SG could avoid specific complications derived from the alteration in intestinal absorption, gut microbiota, or biliary acid circulation associated with RYGB.

Thus, our main aim was to evaluate the effect of both VLCD and SG on NAFLD in high-calorie diet-induced obese rats. To this end, liver steatosis, endothelial damage, oxidative stress, and fibrosis tissue makers were measured. In addition, circulating inflammatory, liver function, and hormonal indicators were also determined.

Material and Methods

Animals

Thirty-five Wistar Han male rats (200–250 g; Harlan Laboratories Models, S.L.), not genetically modified and housed and fed under standard laboratory conditions, were used in this study. European Union Guidelines for Ethical Care of Experimental Animals (EC Directive 86/ 609/EEC for animal experiments) were observed, and approval from our Animal Experimentation Ethics Committee was obtained (CEIC HUGTiP; Ref. EO-12048). Animals were randomized into two main groups: control rats ($n = 7$) which were fed a standard diet (Teklad Global 14% Protein Rodent Maintenance Diet, Teklad Diets Madison WI; Harlan Laboratories) and obese rats which were fed a high-fat diet (HFD) (TD.06414 Harlan Laboratories, Inc. Madison, WI) for 10 weeks. Rats were considered to be obese when the ponderal gain was at least 30% of their initial weight. Both weight and food intake were measured weekly in a fixed interval. Subsequently, obese rats were randomly subdivided into four groups: animals kept in HFD (HFD, $n = 7$), animals fed a very low-calorie diet (VLCD, $n = 7$) (TD.140200 Harlan Laboratories, Inc. Madison), and rats submitted to surgical procedures: a sham operation (sham, $n = 7$) and a sleeve gastrectomy (SG, $n = 7$). After surgery, all the rats continued to be fed an NPO diet for 12–24 h.

Thereafter, the sham group were started on a standard diet ad libitum. In SG group, a liquid diet enriched with glucose was given for 24–48 h depending on clinical evolution. Both the sham and the SG groups were given standard diet after the surgeries and until the end of the study.

Surgery

All surgeries were performed using isoflurane anesthesia administered through a rodent surgical mask, with a veterinary anesthesia machine. In the SG group, the surgical technique was modified and adapted to rats, following the same principles as the procedure devised for humans [14]. The abdominal cavity was accessed through a wide midline incision. After removing nearly 80–90% of the stomach, the gastric tube was closed with a 6/0 non-absorbable polypropylene suture (Prolene®, Ethicon US). The sham procedure consisted in a wide midline laparotomy followed by minimal bowel manipulation. In both cases, the abdominal wall incision was closed with a 2/0 silk suture (PERMA-HAND®, Ethicon US). The procedure time was approximately 45–60 min for the SG group and 5–10 min for the Sham group.

Sample Procurement

All the rats were weighted and then sacrificed on the 16th week of the study. One individual in the sham group was lost during the sacrifice. Blood samples were taken from the carotid artery and processed (centrifuged at 1500–2000×g for 10 min at room temperature and preserved at 4 °C) for plasmatic determination. Liver samples were obtained after perfusion with a saline solution through portal vein to remove any blood content from the liver, in order to avoid alterations in specific protein determination. Five liver tissue samples were procured from each animal: one fixed in formaldehyde and embedded in paraffin for immunochemistry and histological studies, one saturated in an RNA later solution using an RNase-free microfuge tube and immediately preserved at 4 °C for gene expression determination using quantitative reverse transcriptase real-time polymerase chain reaction (qRT-PCR), and three samples frozen in

isopentane using cryogenic vials and preserved at –80 °C for protein measurement by means of Western blot (WB).

Measurements

Histological Study

Steatosis assessment was performed by Oil Red O on frozen slides. For the specific study of fibrosis, 3- μ m paraffin-embedded liver slides were stained with 0.1% Picro-Sirius Red, and the hematoxylin-eosin (H&E) staining process was also performed to study lobular inflammation, cellular ballooning, and cirrhosis.

An expert liver pathologist blindly reviewed and analyzed all the H&E samples following the NASH Clinical Research Network (NASH CRN) Histological Scoring System [15, 16]. The slides stained with Picro-Sirius Red were also reviewed, and a fibrosis grading system (0–4) was performed. On the basis of these data, the SAF score was calculated as described by Bedossa et al. [17]. This score distinguishes between the degree of steatosis (S), the degree of activity (A) (adding lobular inflammation and ballooning), and the fibrosis stage (F), and makes it possible to identify those individuals who could present with some ballooning and inflammation, which are not attributable to NAFLD if steatosis is absent.

Endothelial Damage and Inflammatory and Fibrosis Tissue Markers

For endothelial damage, WB analyses were performed to measure the protein expression of CD31 (diluted 1/200), moesin (diluted 1/300) and p-moesin (diluted 1/200) (Santa Cruz Biotechnology, Dallas, USA); Akt, p-Akt (diluted 1/1000), and p-eNOS (diluted 1/250) (Cell Signaling Technology, Danvers, USA) and eNOS (diluted 1/500) (BD Transduction Labs, USA).

For inflammatory and fibrosis changes, WB analyses of iNOS (diluted 1/500) (BD Transduction Labs, USA) and α SMA (diluted 1/200) (Abcam, Cambridge, UK) were also performed.

For hepatic stellate cell (HSC) activation measurement, the qRT-PCR technique was performed using Taqman gene expression assays for α SMA, type I procollagen (Col1), platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF), PDGF receptor (R-PDGF), and vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) in an 7900HT Fast Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems). Relative changes in gene expression were calculated using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$ method.

Plasmatic Biochemical, Hormonal, and Inflammation Markers

Plasma obtained from the blood samples was used to determine the biochemical parameters (ALP, AST, ALT, LDH, albumin, creatinine, urea, sodium, potassium, glucose, total cholesterol, HDL and triglycerides), the plasmatic hormonal levels (leptin, ghrelin, visfatin and insulin), and the markers of systemic inflammation (IL6, IL10, MCP-1, IL17 α , TNF α), measured using specific ELISA/EIA kits (SigmaAldrich, St. Louis, MO).

Statistical Analysis

All data are expressed as the mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). Mean comparison was performed using an unpaired Student t test, factorial analysis of variance (ANOVA), or the Kruskal–Wallis test when indicated if a lack of homogeneity within groups was detected. A 95% confidence level was considered significant ($p < 0.05$). The statistical analysis was carried out using STATA version 13.0 (StataCorp LP, Texas, USA) and IBM SPSS statistics 21.0. All the statistical aspects of the study were submitted to and reviewed by the Statistical Department at the Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB).

Results

Baseline Characteristics and Systemic Markers

All the determinations evaluating baseline and systemic variations are shown and described in Table 1. Although both the SG group and the VLCD group showed a marked weight loss, only SG experienced a clear improvement in the endocrine-metabolic profile. Moreover, no remarkable differences in inflammatory marker values between the groups were found.

Histology: Steatosis, NASH Activity, and Fibrosis Evaluation (Oil Red, Sirius Red, and H&E)

The liver slides were examined under Oil Red, H&E, and Sirius Red stains to evaluate the presence of steatosis, NASH activity (ballooning and inflammation), and fibrosis, as described

above and according to the SAF score system (Fig. 1). Globally, it was shown that both treatments induced a significant improvement in the NAFLD/NASH histological features.

Endothelial Damage (CD31, Akt/pAkt, Moesin/p-Moesin, and eNOS/p-eNOS Protein Expression in Liver Tissue)

Both vasoconstriction and vasodilatation markers values indicated a clear deleterious effect of HFD on the endothelium which was partially ameliorated after SG was performed. The analysis and results related to endothelial damage are shown in Figs. 2 and 3.

Inflammatory Changes, HSC Activation, and Fibrosis Markers in Liver Tissue (iNOS, α SMA, Coll1, PDGF, R-PDGF, VEGF)

No substantial changes in inflammation and fibrosis markers, as well as in HSC activation measurement, were observed after HFD. Surgery-induced HSC activation that was not clearly correlated with any type of liver damage (Figs. 4 and 5).

Conclusions

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of both sleeve gastrectomy and a very low-calorie diet treatment in a diet-induced NAFLD animal model.

Although both strategies (diet and bariatric surgery) taken together appear to be useful to improve NAFL and NASH progression in histology, our results suggest a slight superiority of bariatric surgery over a very low-calorie diet. A more powerful effect on the improvement not only of some histological aspects but also of endothelial damage, insulin resistance, and some of the cardiovascular risk markers could be the reason for this finding.

Our results also showed that, while a low-calorie diet in experimental conditions (without adherence problems) allows maintenance of a stable weight, surgery groups are the only intervention which induces a significant weight loss. Both the sham and the sleeve groups lost weight in comparison to the HFD group. We believe that weight loss in the sham group could probably be secondary to surgical aggression and a consequence of energy expenditure in the postoperative time period. However, by contrast to the sham group, the SG group is the only one displaying a great weight loss not only by comparison to HFD but also to VLCD.

Despite the effectiveness of SG over diet in weight reduction, after the histological analysis, we found that both

strategies (diet and surgery) can reduce liver fat and NASH progression. Thus, this study cannot establish the exact weight at which the liver fat begins to decrease and, according to histological

results, it would be logical to conclude that both treatments are equally effective in improving steatosis. Nonetheless, the histological improvement does not necessarily reflect the

Table 1 Baseline characteristics and plasmatic markers

		Control	HFD	VLCD	Sham	Sleeve	p value
Body weight (gr)	10weeks	404.143 ± 19.5	489.429 ± 19.5	481.286 ± 19.5	458.500 ± 21.0	492.143 ± 19.5	0.014 ^a
	16weeks	437.000 ± 20.7	544.286 ± 20.7	483.571 ± 20.7	417.500 ± 22.4	375.714 ± 20.7	
IL-6 (pg/mL)		73.2	73.2	73.2	73.2	73.2	No valid
IL-10 (pg/mL)		48.39 ± 13.4	17.18 ± 5.1	15.18 ± 5.9	62.18 ± 26.5	191.50 ± 42.2	0.035 ^b
IL-17α (pg/mL)		28.22 ± 12.2	14.38 ± 4.4	18.22 ± 6.9	25.77 ± 12.8	46.16 ± 34.4	0.8512
MCP-1 (pg/mL)		2304.58 ± 144.1	2631.55 ± 283.9	2628.18 ± 456.0	1814.97 ± 198.8	3588.42 ± 627.2	0.1665
TNFα (pg/mL)		32.65 ± 9.7	24.43 ± 4.8	19.63 ± 8.4	15.96 ± 5.0	31.77 ± 19.0	0.5236
Ghrelin (pg/mL)		6.90	6.90	6.90	6.90	6.90	No valid
Leptin (pg/mL)		7451.81 ± 1265.3	16,029.58 ± 1864.6	14,521.07 ± 4943.8	7476.33 ± 2114.6	2326.54 ± 651.8	0.0029 ^c
Visfatin (ng/mL)		1.84 ± 0.7	3.00 ± 2.1	1.68 ± 0.7	3.96 ± 2.2	3.38 ± 2.0	0.9982
Insulin (UI/L)		1631.76 ± 541.0	1645.85 ± 637.1	1189.85 ± 244.9	936.84 ± 130.2	703.12 ± 380.2	0.0373 ^d
HOMA-IR		34.32 ± 10.4	26.36 ± 3.8	17.78 ± 3.4	14.17 ± 2.5	10.97 ± 5.7	0.0381 ^e
Albumin (g/L)		26.35 ± 0.5	25.97 ± 0.6	25.13 ± 0.4	19.72 ± 1.3	18.3 ± 0.2	0.0016 ^f
AST (U/L)		85.78 ± 8.7	78.25 ± 12.2	62.63 ± 4.4	65.20 ± 8.1	78.00 ± 10.5	0.2470
ALT (U/L)		49.06 ± 6.3	34.05 ± 4.5	23.58 ± 1.9	27.88 ± 4.4	21.75 ± 2.0	0.0706
ALP (U/L)		79.80 ± 4.6	110.00 ± 10.6	76.00 ± 6.9	73.80 ± 3.7	212.67 ± 63.8	0.1002
LDH (U/L)		398.70 ± 108.8	491.17 ± 182.2	513.75 ± 71.1	491.92 ± 133.5	512.95 ± 183.5	0.4154
Total cholesterol (mg/dL)		77.50 ± 2.9	82.71 ± 7.6	63.29 ± 4.5	59.60 ± 6.7	58.71 ± 4.5	0.0294 ^g
HDL (mg/dL)		44.78 ± 1.0	43.73 ± 3.1	43.08 ± 1.7	35.40 ± 3.7	36.72 ± 2.5	0.198
Triglycerides (mg/dL)		160.72 ± 14.3	248.65 ± 43.2	98.58 ± 12.1	64.48 ± 9.2	54.64 ± 6.8	0.0003 ^h
Na (mmol/L)		142.58 ± 0.7	144.07 ± 1.0	143.16 ± 1.3	146.60 ± 1.4	144.72 ± 1.1	0.1685
K (mmol/L)		4.75 ± 0.1	4.51 ± 0.4	4.47 ± 0.2	4.28 ± 0.2	4.35 ± 0.5	0.7613
Creatinine (mg/dL)		0.45 ± 0.0	0.31 ± 0.0	0.31 ± 0.0	0.39 ± 0.0	0.40 ± 0.0	0.0007 ⁱ
Urea (mg/dL)		35.38 ± 1.4	32.83 ± 1.6	38.95 ± 1.1	43.00 ± 2.4	38.12 ± 6.2	0.0762

As shown above, there were no differences in weight between the groups fed a high-fat diet for 10 weeks. However, differences can be found at week 16 after treatments. In the last 6 weeks of the study, the HFD group continued to gain weight, while the weight in the VLCD group remained

stable. Conversely, the sham and the sleeve groups experienced a significant reduction ($p = 0.001$ for sham vs HFD; $p = 0.0001$ for sleeve vs HFD; $p = 0.002$ for sleeve vs VLCD). Concerning the hormonal changes, the sleeve group was the only procedure that induced a significant reduction in the leptin level in plasma ($p = 0.0006$ for sleeve vs HFD; $p = 0.0311$ for sleeve vs VLCD) and an improvement of IR status measured by HOMA-IR index ($p = 0.0261$ for sleeve vs HFD). Moreover, in both surgical groups, a significant decrease in total cholesterol and triglycerides levels was observed ($p = 0.0294$ and $p = 0.0003$ respectively). VLCD also reduced total cholesterol by comparison to HFD ($p = 0.017$). Both surgical groups also presented with a mild reduction in albumin in plasma ($p = 0.0016$). No remarkable differences in inflammatory marker values were found between the groups. However, the sleeve group displayed a mild increase in IL-10 levels by comparison to the HFD and the VLCD groups ($p = 0.0404$ for sleeve vs HFD; $p = 0.0317$ for sleeve vs VLCD)

^a Global difference on weight between groups before and after treatments

^b IL-10: $p = 0.0404$ for sleeve vs HFD; $p = 0.0317$ for sleeve vs VLCD

^c Leptin: $p = 0.0006$ for sleeve vs HFD; $p = 0.0311$ for sleeve vs VLCD

^d Insulin: $p = 0.0098$ for sleeve vs HFD

^e HOMA-IR: $p = 0.0261$ for sleeve vs HFD

^f Albumin: $p = 0.0121$ for sham vs control; $p = 0.0058$ for sleeve vs control; $p = 0.0293$ for sleeve vs HFD

^g Total cholesterol: $p = 0.017$ for VLCD vs HFD; $p = 0.049$ for sham vs control; $p = 0.010$ for sham vs HFD; $p = 0.023$ for sleeve vs HFD

^h Triglycerides: $p = 0.0051$ for sham vs HFD; $p = 0.0166$ for sleeve vs control; $p = 0.0005$ for sleeve vs HFD

ⁱ Creatinine: $p = 0.001$ for HFD vs control; $p = 0.001$ for VLCD vs control

resolution of any other conditions related to NAFLD, evolution of the disease and the main reason for its which in most cases are part of the background or the morbidity and mortality: insulin resistance and diabetes,

	Steatosis (%)	Activity (%) (ballooning + inflammation)	Fibrosis (%)	NASH (%)
Control	0	71.43	28.57	0
HFD	71.43	100	0	71.43
VLCD	0	42.86	28.57	0
Sham	16.67	33.33	33.33	16.67
Sleeve	33.33	100	50	33.33

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16.67% of the sham group and in 33.33% of the sleeve group) and were significantly reduced in the VLCD group. All the groups in the study, including the control group, presented with mild to moderate activity, as well as fibrosis in some cases. However, none of the cases in control and VLCD rats was attributable to

Fig. 1 Histology (a oil red; b Sirius Red; c hematoxylin-eosin) and SAF score (d). The score evaluation of each slide showed that 71.43% of the rats fed a HFD presented with NAFLD and NASH features. The histological alterations were markedly improved in the rats that underwent the sham and the sleeve surgeries (they appeared only in cardiovascular risk, chronic kidney disease, etc. [18, 19].

NAFLD, since there was no presence of steatosis in any of these individuals. In fact, in all the cases with fibrosis, only one case of fibrosis in the sham group is attributable to NAFLD

In fact, regarding this idea, in our study, we found a great difference between a low-calorie diet and bariatric surgery after analyzing plasmatic parameters. According to our data, the intervention on the SG group was the only one able to reduce leptin levels in plasma and improve the IR measured by the HOMA-IR index. These data suggest that only bariatric surgery is able not only to improve steatosis and NASH progression in histology but also reduce the leptin and insulin resistance that is known to be associated with NAFLD [20–22]. In addition, surgery also decreases total cholesterol and triglyceride levels, which contributes to partially reducing the cardiovascular risk associated with NAFLD [4, 23]. This effect could be related to weight loss, as dyslipidemia also improved in the sham and the VLCD groups.

Regarding the endothelial alterations in NAFLD, our highfat-diet-fed model seems to develop the endothelial damage characteristic of the disease, demonstrated by Pasarín et al. [24]. As in that work, we have detected alterations in molecular markers of vasoconstriction and vasodilation in HFD rats. As regards some of them (specifically moesin, p-moesin, and eNOS), the SG group tends to improve this condition. Nevertheless, we believe that our results are not solid enough to conclude the surgery has real benefits regarding the

Fig. 2 Endothelial damage markers in liver tissue. When endothelial damage was evaluated, the HFD rats displayed more alterations in the vasoconstriction and vasodilation markers (* $p < 0.05$ HFD vs control for moesin; ** $p < 0.01$ HFD vs control for p-Akt and eNOS; *** $p < 0.001$ HFD vs control for Akt). These abnormalities improved in the sleeve group, showing a decrease in moesin and p-moesin ($\dagger p < 0.05$)

endothelial damage, since the liver sinusoidal dysfunction related to NAFLD has not been evaluated in depth.

Finally, we evaluated the presence of inflammation, fibrosis, and HSC activation in liver tissue to complement histological data. There is no inflammation or fibrosis demonstrable by these analyses in any of the groups, but we have found more activation of HSC on SG group, which could be a reaction or readjustment of the liver to this surgery. Further studies are needed to assess the reactive nature of this disorder and its long-term consequences. In any case, this increase on HSC activation does not translate to liver damage according to biochemical and histological data.

After the sham operation, some histological parameters improved and the total cholesterol and triglycerides values decreased, even though the gastrointestinal tract was not altered. We believe that these changes could be secondary to

and an increase in eNOS ($\dagger p < 0.05$) compared to the HFD group. The VLCD group also displayed increased Akt protein levels ($\dagger p < 0.05$ vs HFD). In addition, the endothelial dysfunction marker CD31 displayed a significant decrease in VLCD by comparison to HFD ($\dagger\dagger p < 0.01$), but there were no differences between the HFD and the control animals

the weight loss experienced by this group, since VLCD basically also improves histology and the parameters related to dyslipidemia. A long-term follow-up study might confirm the notion that a sham procedure improves some aspects only because of the weight loss and compare it with the effects of SG.

In summary, we restate the fact that both diet and bariatric surgery can improve the histological features of the disease. However, it is worth noting that only bariatric surgery is able

Fig. 3 Endothelial damage markers in liver tissue

Fig.4 Inflammation, fibrosis, and HSC activation markers in liver tissue. Our high-fat-diet-fed model did not induce any relevant changes in inflammatory and/or fibrosis markers, according to the levels of iNOS and αSMA in liver tissue. However, there was a significant decrease in iNOS in the VLCD and the sham groups by comparison to HFD

(††p < 0.01) (Fig. 4). In the qRT-PCR studies, there is a remarkable increase in αSMA in the sleeve group which could suggest HSC activation, which is confirmed by the significantly high mRNA expression of Col1 and PDGF (†p < 0.05 sleeve vs HFD for Col1; ++p

< 0.01 sleeve vs sham, $\dagger\dagger p < 0.01$ sham vs HFD, and $\dagger\dagger\dagger p < 0.001$ sleeve vs control, $\dagger\dagger\dagger$ HFD and $\&\&\&$ VLCD for PDGF) (Fig. 5)
 Fig. 5 Inflammation, fibrosis, and HSC activation markers in liver tissue

not only to improve histological changes but also treat the disease globally by achieving a more substantial weight reduction, improving liver endothelial damage, decreasing insulin resistance, and reducing some of the associated cardiovascular risk indicators. This may be due to the already known metabolic effect of bariatric surgery [25],

which would also be beneficial in NAFLD. According to our data, of the treatments examined, bariatric surgery seems to be the one that could help in treating and reducing the morbidity and mortality related to the disease. For this reason, bariatric surgery displays superiority over a very-low-calorie diet in the treatment of NAFLD disease in our study.

We are aware of the descriptive nature of our findings. Although their clinical relevance is yet unknown, we believe that they could be sufficiently strong to support the idea that bariatric surgery can improve obesity-associated liver

impairment by improving the disease itself and the conditions related to it.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

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